

Research on the Industrial Allocation of Carbon Emissions and the Adjustment of Emission Reduction Policies in China: Based on ZSG-DEA Model

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Summary: With the rapid economic development, environmental pollution caused by energy consumption is becoming increasingly prominent. It is urgent and necessary to clarify emission reduction targets and share the responsibility for carbon emission reduction according to the differences among industries. This paper forecasted the input-output variable values of China's six major industries from 2016 to 2020. Firstly, the original Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) was used to analyze the initial carbon emission allocation results, and the efficiency was found to be low. According to the Zero-sum Gains DEA (ZSG-DEA) model, the initial carbon emission quota was iteratively optimized to calculate the reasonable carbon emission right allocation result. The results showed that the initial carbon emission efficiency of the six major industries in China was relatively low, and the difference in the efficiency value between the

industries was evident. Only the construction industry had realized the effective allocation of the initial carbon emission, while the change amount of the industrial carbon quota was negative after the redistribution, and the emission reduction space was the largest. Accordingly, the end of the paper put forward targeted policy suggestions such as setting up differentiated carbon emission reduction targets among industries, increasing the use of clean energy, improving the carbon emission efficiency and so on.

KEYWORDS: Carbon reduction; Efficiency distribution; Environmental policy; ZSG-DEA; Chinese industry;

1. INTRODUCTION

The Kyoto Protocol gives birth to the international carbon trading market, and the rise of the carbon trading market makes the distribution of carbon emission rights concerned. When the total amount is fixed, the fair distribution of carbon emission rights is the primary factor to avoid conflicts and encourage countries to reduce emissions. At present, there are two main initial allocation methods of carbon emission rights: free distribution and auction [1-3]. The free allocation method allocates the future emission rights according to the past carbon emissions, while the auction method requires enterprises to obtain the emission rights through auction bidding, and the allocation efficiency is relatively higher [4, 5]. For the free allocation of initial carbon emission rights, due to the different stages of economic development in each region and industry, the method of allocating future carbon emissions based on past carbon emission levels only from the perspective of historical fairness is biased. Although auction can promote fairness, enterprises have to face higher financial costs, thus there is a higher resistance to implementation at present [6]. The concept of carbon curse suggests that countries rich in fossil fuels tend to be closely linked to high carbon emissions [7]. Meanwhile, the formulation of carbon reduction policies is closely related to the speed of local economic growth [8]. A price on carbon would slow the rate of warming, but it would also affect the economy to some

extent [9]. In this case, it is of significance to find a more reasonable way of distribution.

The formulation and adjustment of carbon emission policy has become the focus of academic research in the past two years. Zheng et al. (2019) used logarithmic mean decomposition index (LMDI) to estimate seven socioeconomic drivers of the changes in CO₂ emissions in China since 2000 [10]. Li and Qin (2019) proposed a hybrid approach that combines LMDI and decoupling index (LMDI-D) to simulate the challenges China faces in achieving peak CO₂ emissions by 2030 [11]. In order to make a better carbon reduction policy, Chuai and Feng (2019) collected various sources of big data and designed a new methodology to examine carbon emissions in Nanjing city at a high resolution of 300m [12]. Based on a combination of EEIO and DEA, Chen et al. (2019) attempted to examine energy efficiency, carbon dioxide (CO₂) emission efficiency, and related abatement costs of China's regions in 2012 [13]. Without a proper local allocation of carbon credits, China's national plan to reduce emissions cannot be achieved. In order to narrow the knowledge gap in this field in China, Fang et al. (2019) first calculated the overall economic cost of China in 2030, and then proposed a science-based economic cost allocation scheme through the improved ZSG-DEA model [14]. Xie et al. (2019) used data envelopment analysis (DEA) to analyze and evaluate the use of carbon emission rights in Chinese provinces in 2012 [15]. Yu et al. (2020) used the extended log-mean Divisia index model to explore the decoupling relationship between the growth of China's civil aviation sector and carbon emissions and its influencing factors, and predicted future CO₂ emissions [16]. Based on regional spatial differentiation, Liu et al. (2020) analyzed the prediction and driving factors of production CO₂ emissions in Beijing [17]. Feng et al. (2020) proposed a cellular automata model to predict land use scenarios and use these models to estimate China's total carbon and its change between 2000 and 2030 [18].

In recent years, Data Envelopment Model (DEA) is often used to determine carbon emissions sharing and differences among different countries [19, 20], to

achieve a fair and effective distribution of international carbon emission quotas [21, 22]. The Zero-sum Gains DEA (ZSG-DEA) model, which is developed on the basis of the DEA model, can improve the DEA efficiency according to the re-adjustment of distribution [23]. This model can improve the efficiency of DEA according to the re-adjustment of distribution. When a decision-making unit increases or reduces its carbon quota to achieve higher efficiency, another decision-making unit must reduce or increase the same amount of carbon quota accordingly to maintain the total amount [24]. ZSG-DEA is often used to analyze carbon dioxide emission and distribution patterns between different countries. In this model, the determination of carbon emission quotas is no longer subjective, and reasonable carbon emission quotas can be obtained among countries, to achieve global Pareto optimization [25-27].

On the whole, some progress has been made in the research on carbon emission allocation efficiency. However, there are still some limitations: most of the published works focus on carbon emission allocation efficiency at the global, national or regional level. There is little research on the effectiveness of inter-door distribution among industry departments. At the same time, the methodology and data foundation need to be in-depth and refined. This paper studied the allocation model of carbon emission quotas of six major industries in China under different scenarios in 2020, and gave a carbon emission allocation scheme with maximum efficiency, which provided a reference basis for the formulation and adjustment of China's industry carbon emission reduction policies.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Model introduction

Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is a research field of operations research, management science and mathematical economics [28]. It is a quantitative analysis method to evaluate the relative effectiveness of comparable units of the same type by using the method of linear programming according to multiple

input indicators and multiple output indicators [29]. The DEA model assumes that the input (or output) variable of Decision Making Unit (DMU) does not affect the input (or output) of other DMU. However, in some cases, the total amount of input (or output) is fixed, and the input (or output) of each DMU needs to be related to each other to ensure that the total remains the same. The traditional DEA model often assumes that the relevant DMU is independent of each other. At this time, the DEA model can only calculate the relative efficiency and cannot adjust the efficiency. On the issue of carbon emission allocation, the total amount of carbon emissions remains unchanged, and the relative efficiency of each industry allocation can only be calculated by using DEA model, which has obvious limitations in discussing the problem of carbon emission quota allocation under fixed resources. In this case, using the improved ZSG-DEA model, the DEA value can be adjusted to achieve effective allocation [23].

According to this strategy, the authors utilized the ZSG-DEA model of non-expected output input to study the carbon emission efficiency of China's six major industries in different scenarios in 2020. Carbon emissions as the only input variable of ZSG-DEA model, energy consumption and GDP are selected as output variables. The equation of ZSG-DEA model is [30]:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \min \varphi_0 \\ \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i y_{ij} \geq y_{oj}, j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M \\ \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i x_{ik} \left[1 + \frac{x_{ok}(1-\varphi_0)}{\sum_{i \neq 0} x_{ik}} \right] \leq \varphi_0 x_{ok}, k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, R \\ \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i = 1, i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N \\ \lambda_i \geq 0, i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

In this equation: x is the carbon emission quota; y is the GDP and energy intensity; N is the number of DMU; R is the number of input factors; M is the number of output factors; the relative efficiency of DMU_0 is φ_0 , indicating the highest relative efficiency value; λ_i is the ratio of the i th DMU, that is, the carbon emission ratio of each industry; x_{ik} is the input amount of DMU_i ; x_{ok} is the input amount of DMU_0 ; y_{oj} is the output of DMU_0 .

In this model, if the relative efficiency φ_0 of DMU_0 is overinvested, the

excess part will be apportioned to other DMU in proportion $\left[\frac{x_{ik}}{\sum_{i \neq 0} x_{ik}} \cdot (1 - \varphi_0)\right]$, and the quantity DMU_i gets from DMU_0 is $\left[\frac{x_{ik}}{\sum_{i \neq 0} x_{ik}} \cdot x_{ok}(1 - \varphi_0)\right]$. Since all DMU are reducing the proportion of inputs at the same time, after this reallocation, the re-allocation of input k to DMU_i is as follows:

$$x_{ik} = \sum_{0 \neq i} \left[\frac{x_{ik}}{\sum_{i \neq 0} x_{ik}} \cdot x_{ok}(1 - \varphi_0) \right] - x_{ik}(1 - \varphi_i), i = 1, 2, 3 \dots, N \quad (2)$$

Through many iterations, the input variables are allocated reasonably, and finally the DEA efficiency is realized, and the most efficient allocation scheme is obtained.

2.2 Data source and processing

(1) Industry category. According to the China Statistical Yearbook, China's industries are classified into 6 types, including (1) agriculture, forestry, animal husbandry, fishing and water conservancy; (2) construction; (3) industry; (4) wholesale, retail, accommodation and catering; (5) transportation, warehousing and postal services, and (5) other industries.

(2) GDP data of various industries. According to the 2019 GDP table in the China Statistical Yearbook, with an average annual GDP growth rate of 6%, the GDP in 2020 is calculated to be 105 trillion yuan. According to the work plan for controlling greenhouse gas emissions in the 13th five-year Plan, the proportion of the added value of the service sector in 2020 will be increased from 50.5% in 2015 to 56%, and a reasonable estimate of the proportion of GDP in China's six major industries in 2020 will be made. According to the proportion of GDP and the total value of GDP of each industry in 2020, the absolute value of GDP of six major industries in 2020 is calculated, and the results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 proportion and absolute value of GDP in six major industries in 2020

Industry	Percentage of GDP by industry / %	The absolute value of GDP / trillion yuan
Agriculture, forestry, animal husbandry, fishing and water conservancy	9.1	9.555

Industry	28.8	30.24
Construction business	6.7	7.035
Transportation, warehousing and postal services	4.4	4.62
Wholesale, retail and accommodation, catering	11.4	11.97
Other industries	39.6	41.58

(3) Energy consumption in various industries. The 13th five-year Plan for Energy Development proposes that by 2020, the total energy consumption should be controlled within 5 billion tons of standard coal. In terms of energy intensity, according to the planning objectives, the energy consumption per unit of GDP will be reduced by more than 15% during the 13th five-year Plan period, which can meet the binding requirements put forward in the 13th five-year Plan for Energy Development. Taking the energy consumption per unit of GDP of each industry by 15% lower than that in 2015, the energy intensity of each industry in 2015 is calculated according to the total energy consumption of different industries in 2015 and GDP table in the China Statistical Yearbook, so as to estimate the energy intensity of the six major industries in 2020. Finally, the energy consumption of various industries in 2020 is estimated from the GDP estimates given in Sup Table 1, and the results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Energy intensity and energy consumption in 2020

Industry	2015 energy intensity / (10,000 tons of standard coal / 100 million yuan)	Energy intensity in 2020 / (10,000 tons of standard coal / 100 million yuan)	Energy consumption per 10,000 tons of standard coal in 2020
Agriculture, forestry, animal husbandry, fishing and water conservancy	0.13	0.1	9586.37
Industry	1.24	0.99	285834.76
Construction business	0.17	0.13	8963.04

Transportation, warehousing and postal services	1.26	1.01	44623.74
Wholesale, retail and accommodation, catering	0.15	0.12	13280.44
Other industries	0.09	0.07	29605.57

(4) The initial carbon emission quota of each industry. According to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventory prepared by Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), the total carbon emissions of the six major industries in 2015 were calculated to be about 17 billion tons of CO₂. According to the carbon reduction target set in this paper, it is calculated that the total amount to be apportioned in 2020 is about 19 billion tons of CO₂. According to the average proportion of carbon quotas in various industries from 2011 to 2015, the total amount will be allocated proportionally. Table 3 shows the initial carbon quotas for each industry.

Table 3 initial carbon quotas for six major industries

Industry	The proportion of carbon quotas in different industries in different years					Average proportion	Initial carbon quota for 2020 / 10,000 tons of CO ₂
	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015		
Agriculture, forestry, animal husbandry, fishing and water conservancy	0.013	0.013	0.013	0.013	0.013	0.013	24752.674
Industry	0.798	0.796	0.806	0.802	0.792	0.799	1521337.464
Construction business	0.008	0.008	0.007	0.008	0.008	0.008	15232.415
Transportation, warehousing and postal services	0.059	0.063	0.061	0.062	0.065	0.062	118051.218
Wholesale, retail and	0.017	0.017	0.017	0.017	0.018	0.017	32368.882

accommodation,							
catering							
Other industries	0.105	0.103	0.097	0.098	0.105	0.102	192309.241

2.3 Scene setting

The scenario analysis method is used to predict the carbon emission distribution of China's six major industries in 2020. GDP and energy intensity are the main factors affecting the growth of national carbon emissions [31]. In this paper, the development scenario for 2020 is determined according to different GDP and energy intensity standards. Due to the impact of Sino US trade tensions, China's economic growth has slowed down significantly. Under the influence of covid-19 in 2020, the global economy will further decline. On this basis, the authors set the average annual growth rate of GDP at 5%, 5.5% and 6%, while the energy intensity decreases by -15% and -20%. Among them, scenario 1 to scenario 3, scenario 4 to scenario 6 kept the energy intensity unchanged, and the growth rate of GDP increased in turn. Scenario 1 and scenario 4, scenario 2 and scenario 5, scenario 3 and scenario 6 keep the growth rate of GDP unchanged, and the decline of energy intensity increases in turn, corresponding to six development scenarios. Table 4 shows the GDP and energy consumption of six major industries in 2020 under six different scenarios.

Table 4 Scene setting

Scene setting	Scenario 1		Scenario 2		Scenario 3	
		Total		Total		Total
		energy		energy		energy
	GDP/	consumptio	GDP/	consumptio	GDP/	consumptio
Industry	100	n / 10,000	100	n / 10,000	100	n / 10,000
	million	tons of	million	tons of	million	tons of
	yuan	standard	yuan	standard	yuan	standard
		coal		coal		coal
Agriculture,						
forestry,	83608.76	9298.78	84594.72	9408.44	85589.94	9519.12
animal						

husbandry, fishing and water conservancy						
Industry	263947.4 5	277259.72	267060.0 0	280529.25	270201.8 4	283829.57
Construction business	61966.14	8694.15	62696.86	8796.67	63434.47	8900.16
Transportation , warehousing and postal services	40517.80	43293.76	40995.60	43795.46	41477.90	44310.70
Wholesale, retail and accommodatio n, catering	104113.1 4	12882.03	105340.8 7	13033.93	106580.1 8	13187.28
Other industries	361585.9 5	28717.40	365849.8 9	29056.05	370153.9 6	29397.88
Scene setting	Scenario 4		Scenario 5		Scenario 6	
		Total energy consumptio n / 10,000 tons of standard coal		Total energy consumptio n / 10,000 tons of standard coal		Total energy consumptio n / 10,000 tons of standard coal
Industry	GDP/ 100 million yuan		GDP/ 100 million yuan		GDP/ 100 million yuan	
Agriculture, forestry, animal husbandry, fishing and water conservancy						
Industry	263947.4 5	260950.32	267060.0 0	264027.53	263947.4 5	277259.72
Construction	61966.14	8182.73	62696.86	8279.22	61966.14	8694.15

business						
Transportation						
, warehousing	40517.80	40738.85	40995.60	41219.26	40517.80	43285.03
and postal						
services						
Wholesale,						
retail and	104113.1	12124.26	105340.8	12267.23	104113.1	12882.03
accommodatio	4		7		4	
n, catering						
Other	361585.9	27028.15	365849.8	27346.87	361585.9	28717.40
industries	5		9		5	

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Calculation of initial DEA

In this paper, the initial allocation efficiency of carbon emission quotas in six major industries in China from 2016 to 2020 was calculated by using DEAP2.1 software (take scenario 1 as an example). The results were shown in Table 5. There is a large gap in the initial efficiency value of the six major industries (column 4 of Table 5), only the construction industry had reached the highest efficiency value 1 and achieved effective distribution. The efficiency of agriculture, forestry, animal husbandry, fishing and water conservancy was relatively high, close to 1. The average efficiency of distribution in the six major industries was only 0.741, which was relatively low. Especially in industry, the initial efficiency value was only 0.351, the efficiency value was seriously low, far away from the effective boundary, and there still needed some improvement in the work. At present, the allocation efficiency of most industries was low, and the allocation efficiency needed to be further improved. In order to realize the effective allocation of carbon emission quotas in six major industries in China, this study used the ZSG-DEA model to reallocate carbon emission quotas on the basis of DEA model.

Table 5 Scenario 1 Carbon Emission quota efficiency value and quota Adjustment result of ZSG-DEA Model

Industry	ZSG-DEA efficiency value				Final DEA efficien cy value	Final adjusted carbon quota / 10,000 tons of CO2	Target carbon reductio n / 10,000 tons CO2	Intensi ty of carbon emissio n reducti on
	Initi al valu e	First iteratio n	Second iteratio n	Third iterati on				
Agriculture, forestry, animal husbandry, fishing and water conservancy	0.91 2	0.95633 01	0.979	0.999	1	130493.1 98	102906. 343	-3.154
Industry	0.35 1	1	1	0.982	0.993	1011635. 580	- 683895. 024	0.447
Constructio n business	1	1	1	1	1	97975.16 3	80998.6 37	-4.348
Transportati on, warehousing and postal services	0.70 6	0.26491 44	0.80353 71	1	1	160202.8 22	28634.7 39	0.068
Wholesale, retail and accommodat ion, catering	0.86 9	0.921	0.985	1	1	163179.2 82	127104. 163	-2.718
Other industries	0.50 8	0.603	1	1	1	558579.7 91	344251. 142	-0.831
Total	—	—	—	—	—	2122065. 836	0	—
Average efficiency value	0.74 1	0.823	0.951	0.997	0.999	—	—	—

3.2 Redistribution process and result Analysis based on ZSG-DEA Model

Based on the ZSG-DEA model (equation 1), the carbon emission quotas of six major industries were readjusted. According to the proportional reduction equation (2) and iterative analysis, the effective distribution of carbon emissions was realized. The specific iterative process and adjustment results were shown in Table 1, taking scenario 1 as an example. Comparison indicates that the efficiency values of the six major industries were higher than the initial value. After the third iteration, the average DEA efficiency value was 0.997, and almost all configuration efficiency values were close to 0.999. To achieve the expected most effective efficiency, the model was further adjusted. After the fourth iteration, the efficiency value of all industries except industry was 1, which reaches the unified effective boundary of ZSG-DEA. Comparing the initial efficiency value with the allocation efficiency after the fourth iteration, the average efficiency value increased from 0.741 to 0.999. Column 9 of Table 1 showed the final adjusted carbon quotas for each industry. The target carbon emission reduction of each industry was shown in column 10 of Table 1. From a numerical point of view, except for industry, the adjustment results of agriculture, forestry, animal husbandry, fishing, water conservancy, construction, transportation, warehousing and postal services, wholesale, retail and accommodation, catering were all positive. This showed that according to current forecasts, these five industries could still achieve DEA effectiveness by increasing their carbon emissions. To achieve the effectiveness of DEA, industry must reduce the corresponding amount of carbon emissions, promote industrial low-carbon development, actively control carbon emissions, strengthen the industrial sector to cope with climate change, and establish a low-carbon industrial development system that is divided into stages, regions, sectors and enterprises. In addition, it is also very important to rationally optimize the industrial structure, increase technology investment and clean energy utilization.

In this paper, the ZSG-DEA model was used to improve the low utilization

efficiency of carbon emission quotas in some industries, and the reasonable allocation of carbon quotas among industries was realized. The authors compared the carbon reduction intensity of various industries compared with 2015 (column 8 of Table 1), and found that although all industries have achieved DEA effectiveness, there was a large gap in the emission reduction potential of each industry. Only the industry had exceeded the carbon reduction targets of the 13th five-year Plan to Control greenhouse Gas emissions, and the other five industries still had more room for improvement. This might be related to the efforts made by the ZSG-DEA model to adjust industrial quotas in order to achieve effective allocation. Besides, we compared the target carbon emissions of different industries in different scenarios, as shown in Table 6. Table 6 showed that from scenario 2 to scenario 6, the adjustment of industrial carbon emission quota was all negative, while the other five major industries were all positive. This was consistent with scenario 1, which showed that industry needed to focus on reducing emissions under this allocation.

Table 6 Target carbon emission reduction for each industry under different scenarios

Scene setting	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4	Scenario 5	Scenario 6
Industry	Target carbon emission reduction / 10,000 tons of CO ₂					
Agriculture, forestry, animal husbandry, fishing and water conservancy	10.25832	10.37929	10.5014	11.19089	11.32286	11.45607
Industry	-68.1747	-68.9787	-69.7901	-74.3724	-75.2494	-76.1347
Construction business	8.074427	8.169643	8.265756	8.808466	8.912338	9.017188
Transportation, warehousing and postal services	2.854481	2.888142	2.92212	3.113979	3.150701	3.187767
Wholesale, retail and	12.6705	12.81992	12.97074	13.82236	13.98536	14.14989

accommodation,						
catering						
Other industries	34.317	34.72168	35.13016	37.43673	37.8782	38.32382

3.3 Comparison of carbon emission distribution efficiency

Some scholars have used the ZSG-DEA model to redistribute the responsibility of carbon reduction in China at the provincial level [32]. This study directly analyzed the main body of emission reduction from the perspective of industry, and made an in-depth and detailed analysis of the methodology and data basis. Pan et al. (2015) used the ZSG-DEA model to study the CO₂ emission limits of six major industries in China in 2020 [33], and our research was the most comparable. Two papers (this study takes scenario 1 as an example) used the ZSG-DEA model to study China's carbon emission reduction from the industry level. The difference in CO₂ emissions between the two papers after the fourth iteration in 2020 was shown in Fig 1. Although the data processing methods of the two articles were different, after the fourth iteration, the change trend of the target carbon emission reduction of the two papers in 2020 was similar. However, in this paper, the target carbon emission reduction of most industries after the fourth iteration in 2020 was less than that of Pan et al. (2015). There may be two reasons for this difference: first, Pan et al. (2015) continued the 12th five-year Plan as the overall goal of carbon emissions allocation, while this paper directly took the directive in the 13th five-year Plan as the goal. Goal setting was more reasonable and in line with existing policies. Second, in terms of data processing, Pan et al. (2015) directly used the average growth rate of previous years to calculate. This paper used the method of scenario analysis to estimate the GDP data and energy consumption of various industries in 2020, and the study was more refined.

Fig.1 Comparison of the trend of target carbon emission reduction in 2020 after four iterations in two articles

4. CONCLUSION

From the point of view of allocation efficiency improvement, based on the ZSG-DEA model and scenario analysis method, we adjusted and optimized the allocation efficiency of carbon emission quotas in six major industries in China from 2016 to 2020, and formulated an effective carbon emission reduction allocation plan. The main conclusions were as follows: first of all, the initial carbon emission efficiency of the six major industries in China is low, and the difference between industries from 2016 to 2020 is evident. Only the construction industry has achieved the effective distribution of initial carbon emissions. The industrial efficiency value is only 0.351, and the allocation efficiency is seriously low, which needs to be improved urgently. Second, the ZSG-DEA model is used to redistribute carbon emission quotas among industries, to consider efficiency maximization. After four iterations, the efficiency of carbon emission quota reallocation in each industry is significantly improved, which basically reaches the unified effective boundary of ZSG-DEA and achieves limited allocation. Third, from the point of view of the final

adjustment, only the industrial carbon quota is changed to a negative value after reallocation, and the room for emission reduction is the largest, which can be compensated by the corresponding increments of the other five industries to keep the total carbon emissions unchanged.

Based on the conclusion of this paper, the following suggestions were put forward: first, to establish different carbon emission reduction targets among industries, improve the carbon emission efficiency of various industries, and realize the reasonable and effective allocation of carbon emission quotas among industries. The second is to encourage the development of new energy and increase the use of clean energy. In the process of accelerating carbon emission reduction and sustainable development, we should adjust the industrial structure, speed up industrial upgrading, rationally optimize the allocation of resources, and improve carbon emission efficiency.

At present, global researches on carbon emissions allocation were mainly focused on inter-regional, and there was not much consideration for inter-industry. Compared with previous studies, we were more detailed in terms of allocation methods and data benchmarks from the perspective of the industry, which could provide a reference basis for the adjustment of carbon emission reduction policies in China's industry. Future research can take into account industrial development plans, government support for related projects and other factors, so as to better match national strategies and policies, balance fairness and efficiency, rather than focusing on historical output factors.

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